

Practice effects on low intensity synchronous handcycling in able-bodied men: A biophysical approach

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Abstract The aim of the study was to investigate the effects of short practice on the physiology and biomechanics of low-intensity synchronous handcycling. Twelve non-disabled participants handcycled on a motorized treadmill at 1.94 m/s. The practice program consisted of a pre-test, three practice sessions and a post-test. All sessions were 12 minutes long. A breath-by-breath gas analyzer measured physiological parameters. The 3D force components as well as the crank and handle angle were measured at the left side by an instrumented handcycle and fraction of effective force was calculated. Other than a significant increase of heart rate from the fourth to the 12th minute in both pre- and post-test ($P < 0.01$), no significant effects of practice were found. No practice effects on the mean force components nor the fraction of effective force were found. However, a small change in effective force profile can be recognized.

Keywords Handcycle, practice, physiology, biomechanics, force profile

Introduction

The handcycle and its settings has been subject for studies for over four decades. However, a lack of reports on short-term practice on daily handcycling seems to be present even though knowledge on short-term learning effects might have implications for early rehabilitation. We therefore aim to investigate the effects of a practice time of about 36 minutes on the physiology and force application during low intensity synchronous handcycling. We hypothesize that the total practice time is too short to cause structural metabolic changes; therefore, we will see no changes in the physiological parameters. However, because of the motor learning in an early stage, we do expect that people can learn to handcycle more efficient in terms of force application.

Methods

Twelve inexperienced able-bodied men (age: 23.9 ± 1.2 years, mass: 78.6 ± 9.1 kg, height: 1.81 ± 0.05 m and arm length: 0.64 ± 0.02 m) rode an instrumented add-on handcycle on a motorized

leveled treadmill at 1.94 m/s. The total program consisted of a pre-test, three exercise sessions and a post-test. All five sessions had the same procedure, three blocks of 4-minute exercise with two minutes rest in-between. In the pre- and post-tests, the conditions were the same; the participants rode the handcycle without any additional resistance (± 15 W) and with a gear ratio of 0.741. During the practice sessions the resistance and gear was changed, see Kraaijenbrink, Vegter et al. (2017). In every session, a breath-by-breath gas analyzer was used and VO₂ (ml/kg/min), VCO₂ (ml/kg/min), VE (L/kg/min) and HR (bpm) were measured. Energy Expenditure (W/kg) was calculated using VO₂ and VCO₂ according to Garby and Astrup (1987). The 3D forces, handlebar angle and crank angle were recorded at the left handle and transformed to the tangential, radial and mediolateral force component (van Drongelen, van den Berg et al., 2011). Fraction of effective force was calculated as the ratio tangential to total force. Mean values were used for further statistical analysis. Practice effects were analyzed with a repeated measures ANOVA ($p < 0.05$) with test (pre/post) and time (fourth, eighth and twelfth minute) as within-subject factors.

Results

Other than a significant increase of the heart rate from the fourth to the twelfth minute, no significant effects were found for any of the physiological variables (Table 1). Significant effects on neither of the force components nor fraction of effective force were found. However, a small change in the force profile can be seen (Figure 1).

Table 1. Mean (SD) of the main physiological and biomechanical variables (n=12)

	Pre-Test			Post-Test			Test	Time	Test*Time
	4 th minute	8 th minute	12 th minute	4 th minute	8 th minute	12 th minute	F (df)	F (df)	F (df)
Energy Expenditure (W/kg)	4.90 (0.65)	4.85 (0.78)	4.77 (0.64)	4.94 (0.79)	4.79 (0.68)	4.93 (0.70)	0.075 (1,11)	1.477 (2,22)	0.447 (2,22)
Heart Rate (bpm)	84 (8)	85 (8)	86 (7)	83 (8)	84 (7)	86 (7)	0.116 (1,11)	5.969 (2,22)**	1.633 (2,22)
Ventilation (L/kg/min)	0.27 (0.06)	0.26 (0.05)	0.26 (0.04)	0.25 (0.03)	0.26 (0.03)	0.26 (0.04)	0.477 (1,11)	0.056 (2,22)	0.669 (1.3,14.3)
Fraction of Effective Force (%)	55 (10)	58 (8)	57 (10)	62 (9)	61 (10)	62 (11)	3.597 (1,11)	0.536 (1.3,15.1)	1.265 (2,22)

Note: bold=significant; *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001

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Figure 1. Effective force profile (n=12, bold=mean value).

Conclusion and discussion

As expected, no relevant changes in any of the physiological parameters were found. However, we did expect to see a change in the force application, due to motor learning. Since we did not see any effects of practice on the effectiveness of the force application, we can conclude that this amount of practice is not sufficient to cause any changes.

References

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